

Thai Arts and Culture the Formation of Thai Identity Letter Font Designed

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Abstract—The purpose of the analysis of Thai Arts and Culture which concerning the formation of Thai identity letter font designed is to identify The Aumphawa local community identity so as to select the suitable letter font which can applicable to the computer software usage. The populated survey was from the group of local people who live in Aumphawa sub-district. The methodological is cluster sampling from 100 surveyed, those 50 were from people who have household registration done in Aumphawa sub-district and other from people who live outside. In order to analyze and design the Thai identity letter font computer software designed for both Thai and English language version, the analysis had been completed by compiling of document and field survey from local people's opinion on their Arts and Culture identity. The out-put will be submitted to the experts for evaluation.

Keywords—Thai Arts, Design, Font, Identity.

I. INTRODUCTION

AUMPHAWA sub-district community is a waterfront and orchard community which located in the middle of Aumphawa district Samutsongkram province, 72km. away from the west side of Bangkok. This area was so called “Bang Chang” which was part of Rajaburi town in Authaya era and has been transformed to be Aumphawa district in Samutsakorn province since 1940.

The Aumphawa community is one of the towns related to Chakri Dynasty as The King Rama I and The Queen were resigned there during tenure for capital procurement rank before promoted to Chakri Throne, besides The King Rama II and the Queen were also born there.

The Aumphawa community still obtains it symbolic community since then by having many of architectures, historical places, arts and culture maintain in good condition. Apart from this, Aumphawa area was also surrounding with orchards located close to canal routes where has been perfectly designed utilizing until nowadays.

In the past, Aumphawa was one of the important commercial water trail in Mae Klong river thereafter, in 1977 there were many of roads and canals construction projects in the upper area of Mae Klong river had been taken place which caused the change of Eco-system decay from abundance of natural resources, the growth of town with commercials and job opportunity turn to an empty town with the relocation of population [1].

In 2002 Aumphawa sub-district was selected to be a part of

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“The Conservation and Development of River, Ditch and Canal Pilot Project” which deliberated from “The Master plan and Operational plan of Conservation and Development of River, Ditch and Canal in the West basin area”

In order to determine the regulatory in using of canals, land banks and to set up the developing plan to promote Eco tourism for the effectiveness of Aumphawa canal trail using, Aumphawa sub-district has assigned Chulalongkorn University, The Faculty of Architecture to do the participatory action research from authorities concerned such as management executives of Aumphawa sub-district, representatives from Aumphawa public community, Chai Pattana Foundation – Samutsongkram Office, Office of Natural Resources and Environmental Policy and Planning, Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment, Department of Industrial Promotion, Ministry of Industry.

The consequence from the cooperation of government agencies and private sectors had brought The Aumphawa community received The Conservative Community from The Architecture Society of Thailand in 2002, and The Honorable Mention Reward from UNESCO Asia-Pacific Heritage Award in 2008 respectively.

As a result of The Arts Environment Project, Thailand Cultural Environment Project – The Aumphawa Canal Community Thailand and the continually implemented of business reorganization, improvement of social and culture which brought it to the prototype study of other communities, Aumphawa community now turn into rapid changed as one of the culture tourism market in Thailand [2].

Since 2010 number of tourist from Europe make 20% increment to Aumphawa tourism industry, some of them carry on drinking culture to Aumphawa which has been done in Pattaya or Phuket. For this reason it has caused more completion among bar, public houses and other kind of businesses. So as to support the tourism and to assist the business owner in the community and the tourist to bare in mind of Aumphawa unique community culture, 1st Lieutenant Patcharodom Ounsuwan, former Mayor of Aumphawa sub-district was presented the idea of Native product under Aumphawa brand logo [3].

Nowadays most of Organizations business strategy is to have their Organization the great image, unique from others and a trustworthy from the public domain, concerning this Identity system has not been created officially only to use for Organization but it also be used to created product brand logo.

In general the creation of a perfected and effectiveness of Identity system will consist of three main things such as name, mark and letter [4], except from those the prototype letter

should be qualified with clear and concise characteristic so as to create more powerful communications both in writing and typing [5].

At present days the continually developed of Thai letter font computer software has been created to use generally both open source software and commercial software [6]. In contrary, Thailand education system never set off a specific course study in the area of Thai identity letter font computer software creation before as well as the lack of developer or expertise which caused the limitation to communicate in Thai letter font computer software.

The purpose of this research is to bring art, culture and identity of THE Aumphawa community to create and develop Thai letter font for communications, knowledge dissemination and to represent the community unifying. Moreover, is to encourage people from various community cultures to realize on the important of their local Art and Culture value which should be deserved only ever for their community.

II. OBJECTIVES

1. To searching for the important of local Art, Culture and Identity of The Aumphawa sub-district community.
2. To analyze and design the identity letter font of The Aumphawa sub-district community.
3. To create the identity letter font which applicable to computer software.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Population of Study

The survey had been made from 50 local people who live in Aumphawa sub-district, Samut Songkram province by Cluster Sampling, and another 50 by Accidental Sampling. Total survey = 100 samples.

B. Questionnaire

The questionnaire had been made from public opinion on art, culture and identity of the local community and from their satisfaction after evaluation of the Identity letter font by 5 rating scales as follows: most satisfaction, more satisfaction, moderate level, less level, and the least [7].

C. Research Tools

The guideline of letter font design was done from 6 typeface designs and from 1 set of Identity letter font which was composed from Thai letter and Latin letter.

Fig. 1 Typeface 1

Fig. 2 Typeface 2

Fig. 3 Typeface 3

Fig. 4 Typeface 4

Fig. 5 Typeface 5

Fig. 6 Typeface 6

Fig. 7 Set of Thai letter Font

Fig. 8 Set of Latin letter Font

IV. RESULT

The output from public opinion on Art, Culture and Identity of community which was made from 50 local people by

Cluster Sampling, and another 50 by Accidental Sampling. Total survey = 100 samples are as follow:

TABLE I
 PUBLIC OPINION FROM GROUP OF GENERAL STATUS – IDENTIFIED NUMBER AND PERCENTAGE (N = 100)

Description	Percentage
1. Gender:	
Male	33
Female	67
2. Age:	
Under 15	1
15-25	35
26-35	24
36-45	20
46-55	11
Beyond 55	9
3. Education level:	
Under Primary	1
Primary	11
Secondary school	4
High school	13
Diploma	9
Undergraduate	55
Graduate	6
Postgraduate	1
4. Profession: (local people)	
Government employee	5
Student	14
State Enterprise employee	-
Local business man	1
Retired people	5
Private sector employee	12
Others e.g. University employee	13
Profession: (outside Aumphawa)	
Government employee	5
Student	13
State Enterprise employee	3
Local business man	21
Retired people	2
Private sector employee	5
Others e.g. University employee	1
5. Public: (who knows Aumphawa in number of year)	
1-2	10
3-4	12
5-6	12
7-8	5
9-10	6
More than 10	55
6. Channels:	
Self-acknowledge	59
Informed by others	25
Public Relations	13
Other e.g. web site	3

Table I shows the survey output on Art, Culture and Identity of community from 50 local people by Cluster Sampling, and another 50 by Accidental Sampling. Total survey = 100 samples. Most of survey samples were from Female with age range between 15 to 25 with Undergraduate education background of which from local people and outside whose self-acknowledge of Aumphawa.

From Table II, most of the survey result from 100 samples of public opinion on the outstanding of Arts and Culture of Aumphawa were identified in percentage respectively as follow:

- Wall Stucco image at Bangkrapom temple at 69 %
- Statue of King Rama II at 63 %
- Utasik Pagoda at Kasem Soranaram temple at 62 %

TABLE II
PUBLIC OPINION ON ARTS AND CULTURE OF AUMPHAWA – IDENTIFY IN PERCENTAGE (N=100)

Description	No	Yes	
		Similarity	Difference
1. Wall painting at Kasem Soranaram temple	20	33	47
2. Waterfront buildings	3	48	49
3. Utasik Pagoda at Kasem Soranaram temple	9	29	62
4. Ancient Houseboat at Hua Lam community	14	30	56
5. Aumphawa Government Municipal Building	11	44	45
6. Wall Stucco image at Bangkrpom temple	8	23	69
7. The King Rama II Monument	10	27	63
8. Oboe-based Thai Orchestra	10	50	40
9. Others (please identify.....)	-	-	-

TABLE III
PUBLIC OPINION ON IDENTITY OF AUMPHAWA COMMUNITY– IDENTIFY IN PERCENTAGE (N=100)

Description	No	Yes	
		Similarity	Difference
1. Farming community / Local generous society	13	44	43
2. Waterfront city / Floating market	3	33	64
3. Perfect Eco-system Environment / Flyer fire	9	13	78
4. Ancient Wooden house / Houseboat at Hua Lam community	4	35	61
5. Historical places of the imperial of Chakri Dynasty	13	23	64
6. Origin of Arts / City of Artist	7	38	55
7. Others (please identify.....)	-	-	-

From Table III, the survey outputs from 100 samples of public opinion on the unique of Identity of Aumphawa community were identified in percentage respectively as follow:

- Perfect Eco-system Environment / Flyer fire at 78 %
- Waterfront city / Floating market and Historical places of the imperial of Chakri Dynasty at 64 % respectively.

From Table IV, the survey result of public opinion from the group of general status has been done from 50 local people by Cluster Sampling and another 50 by Accidental Sampling. Total survey = 100 samples. Most of survey samples were from Female with age range between 15 to 25 with Undergraduate education background of which from local people and outside whose self-acknowledge of Aumphawa.

From Table V, The top level of Letter font Satisfaction survey were Typeface 2 at 38 % followed by Typeface 1 at 26 %, Typeface 5 at 12 %, Typeface 4 at 11 %, Typeface 3 at 10 % and Typeface 6 at 3 % respectively.

TABLE IV
PUBLIC OPINION FROM GROUP OF GENERAL STATUS – IDENTIFIED NUMBER AND PERCENTAGE (N = 100)

Description	Percentage
1. Gender:	
Male	45
Female	55
2. Age:	
Under 15	2
15-25	42
26-35	9
36-45	17
46-55	11
Beyond 55	19
3. Education level:	
Under Primary	15
Primary	5
Secondary school	5
High school	10
Diploma	4
Undergraduate	53
Graduate	8
Postgraduate	-
4. Profession: (local people)	
Government Officer	3
Student	23
Government employee/University employee	-
State Enterprise employee	-
Local business man	3
Retired people	8
Private sector employee	11
Others e.g. temple patronage	2
Profession: (outside Aumphawa)	
Government Officer	12
Student	17
Government employee/University employee	11
State Enterprise employee	-
Local business man	-
Retired people	5
Private sector employee	5
Others (please identify.....)	-
5. Public: (who knows Aumphawa in number of year)	
1-2	4
3-4	15
5-6	8
7-8	7
9-10	10
More than 10	56
6. Channels:	
Self-acknowledge	68
Informed by others	20
Public Relations	12
Other (please identify.....)	-

TABLE V
LETTER FONT SATISFACTION LEVEL – IDENTIFIED NUMBER IN PERCENTAGE (N = 100)

Guideline of design	Frequency
Typeface 1	26
Typeface 2	38
Typeface 3	10
Typeface 4	11
Typeface 5	12
Typeface 6	3

TABLE VI
LETTER FONT SATISFACTION LEVEL – IDENTIFIED NUMBER IN PERCENTAGE
(N = 100)

Description	N=1	N=2	N=3	N=4	N=5	\bar{X}	S.D.
Identity model	4	5	4	4	5	4.40	0.55
Unity model	5	4	4	5	4	4.40	0.55
Clear and Remarkable model	5	4	4	4	5	4.40	0.55
Figure fit to minimized and enlarged size model	5	4	5	4	5	4.60	0.55
Applicable to Public Relations model	4	4	5	5	5	4.60	0.55
\bar{X}	4.60	4.20	4.40	4.40	4.80	4.48	0.55
S.D.	0.49	0.40	4.49	4.49	0.40		

From Table VI, Reviewing by 5 experts, the result of The Aumphawa Identity Letter font was concluded as follow:

Model 2 obtain Average rate = 4.48 and Standard Deviation = 0.55 which applicable to be used in Public Relations. The figure fit to minimized and enlarged size model obtain average rate = 4.60 and Standard Deviation = 0.55 and the Identity model, Unity model, Clear and remarkable model obtain average rate = 4.40 and Standard Deviation = 0.55

V.CONCLUSION

1. The Arts and Culture of Aumphawa sub-district community is The Wall Stucco image at Bangkrpom temple, and Identity of the community is The Eco-system Environment / Flyer fire which represent an indication of fruitful natural resources.
2. The connectivity of The Eco-system Environment / Flyer fire to the analysis of Aumphawa Identity can be considered as Personality Theory of Kobayashi concept which showing the way of life in kindness, generosity, simplexes and peaceful in the nature.
3. The creation of The Aumphawa Identity Letter font was inspired from The King Rama II Monument.
4. The effectiveness of The Aumphawa Identity Letter font was considered in the good average rating at 4.48 which applicable for using in Public Relations. The figure fit to minimize and enlarge size model obtain average rating at 4.60, and the Identity model, Unity model, Clear and remarkable model obtain average rating at 4.40 respectively.

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